

Leveraging Machine Learning Algorithms for Phishing Website URL Detection

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Abstract— There is an increasing need for strong detection techniques due to the growing intricacy of phishing strategies. Using machine learning methods, this session explores the field of phishing website detection. Our method uses CatBoost's discriminative capacity to examine the features of phishing websites with the goal of improving accuracy and efficiency. The suggested approach reduces security risks in a time when cyber-attacks are a common occurrence by offering users a smooth interface to determine the legality of URLs. Through combining knowledge from several detection techniques, such as similarity-based, list-based, and machine learning-based methods, we want to strengthen the defense against phishing attempts that are always evolving. By conducting a comprehensive analysis of the existing state of affairs and identifying areas that require further investigation, our project aims to enhance the field of phishing detection and protect people and organizations from financial losses and privacy violations.

Keywords— CatBoost, Phishing, Machine Learning Techniques, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, SVM, ML

I. INTRODUCTION

The Malicious actors frequently use phishing websites as a ruse to impersonate reputable websites and online platforms. Phishing is the practice of creating phony websites that closely mimic real ones in an effort to trick people into disclosing personal information when they shouldn't. These dishonest websites are frequently used by attackers to fool users into divulging credit card details, login credentials, and other private information that may be used for illegal gain. Phishing attacks are mostly directed on online banking portals, e-commerce platforms, and electronic payment systems. They take advantage of these targets' weaknesses and are difficult to identify. Enhancing detection and preventive techniques is therefore essential.

The "blacklist" technique is one way to spot phishing websites; it entails collecting URLs that antivirus databases have reported because of questionable activity linked to their IP addresses. In order to avoid detection, attackers use a variety of strategies, including obfuscating URLs and using flux to dynamically switch hosting proxies or algorithms constraint of this approach is its incapacity to immediately detect recently initiated phishing attempts

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Tanimu et. al (2022) address the escalating threat of phishing attacks, highlighting the inadequacy of current detection methods. They propose a novel approach

leveraging machine learning to enhance efficacy and accuracy. Their review critiques existing methods and emphasizes the need for more effective solutions. The authors underscore the limitations of current techniques while hinting at their ongoing work, which involves image visualization of website code and feature extraction from malicious URLs.[1]

Zieni, et al. (2023) emphasize the persistent threat of phishing, noting its evolving tactics and detrimental impact. Their survey underscores the significance of phishing detection, given its continued success. They offer a comprehensive review of detection methods, categorizing them into list-based, similarity-based, and machine learning-based approaches. Each category is explored in terms of proposed methods and assessment datasets, highlighting research gaps. This review provides valuable insights into the current state of phishing detection, guiding future research directions.[2]

Parvathy (2022) addresses the urgent need for robust phishing detection methods amid escalating cyber threats. Focusing on machine learning algorithms, the paper surveys existing literature, emphasizing the importance of effective detection strategies. It highlights the evolution of phishing tactics and the inadequacy of traditional detection methods. Parvathy's review sets the stage for proposing novel approaches grounded in machine learning, offering potential solutions to enhance detection accuracy and resilience against phishing attacks.[3]

Abbas Helmi et al. (2023) contributes to the discourse on online phishing detection, particularly emphasizing machine learning approaches. Their literature review highlights the persistent and evolving nature of phishing threats, necessitating advanced detection strategies. Critically assessing existing methodologies, the paper identifies shortcomings in traditional detection methods. By aligning with the trend of employing machine learning for enhanced detection capabilities, Abbas Helmi et al. underscore the importance of staying ahead of evolving cyber threats. This review serves as a foundation for proposing innovative solutions in the field of online phishing detection.[5]

Pournamy (2023) contributes to the discourse on phishing detection, focusing on machine learning algorithms. The literature review underscores the persistent threat of phishing and the imperative for advanced detection mechanisms. It critiques existing methods, noting their limitations in effectively combating evolving phishing tactics. Pournamy's work aligns with the broader trend of leveraging machine

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learning to enhance detection accuracy and adaptability. By highlighting gaps in current approaches, this review lays the groundwork for proposing innovative solutions in phishing detection. [4]

III. METHODOLOGY

1) DATA SET DESCRIPTION

- a) The offered dataset includes features extracted from URLs to classify websites as phishing or non-phishing. The characteristics fit into the following groups:
 - i) Address bar-related features
 - ii) Domain-related features
 - iii) HTML and JavaScript-based features

1. Address bar-related features

1.1. Domain of the URL

Some properties of the URL domain must be extracted and taken into consideration as features. Out of all the options, the following decisions have been made for this project.

1.2. Using IP Address

Using IP IP addresses found in URLs may indicate attempts at identity theft. An IP address found in the domain component of the URL is considered evidence of phishing activity and is assigned systems.

Fig 1 Architecture of Phishing Detection

In absence of an IP Address, the domain is considered valid and given a rating of -1.

- 1.3. A URL's ability to contain the "@" symbol is verified. The real address appears after "@" in URLs, with anything preceding it usually ignored. It is rated as 1 (phishing) if "@" is present; if not, it is rated as -1 (legitimacy).
- 1.4. Phishing scammers frequently employ URL shortening services to shorten URLs and divert consumers to dangerous websites.

- 1.5. If a URL has a "." in its domain, it is checked. Real URLs typically don't use dashes. Prefixes and suffixes, divided by dots, are frequently added by phishers to trick consumers into believing they are visiting a trustworthy website.
- 1.6. One way to identify "/" redirection in URLs is to look for "/" symbols in the URL route. If these symbols are found, users can be routed to an alternate website.
- 1.7. The credibility of a website can be influenced by the existence of a favicon. The appearance of a favicon in the address bar can indicate a phishing attempt.

2. Domain-related features

In some domains, data extraction is a specific function.

- 2.1. Examining DNS records is determining if a possible phishing website has an empty or untraceable DNS record. If the record is missing, it receives a rating of 1 (phishing); if it is present, it receives a value of -1 (legitimacy).
- 2.2. Web traffic analysis uses indicators like page views and visitor count to determine how popular a website is.
- 2.3. Given the short lifespan of phishing attempts, the Age of Domain is an important consideration. Domains must be active for at least a year in order to be eligible for this project.
- 2.4. In this context, the time interval between a domain's registration and expiration is referred to as its age.

3. HTML and JavaScript based Features

The features in the dataset come from HTML and JavaScript.

- 3.1. IFrame Redirection is the process of using the HTML element IFrame to incorporate another website inside the existing one.
- 3.2. Phishers take advantage of this to conceal or eliminate frame borders, frequently giving instructions to web browsers on how to distinguish themselves using the "frameborder" function.
- 3.3. JavaScript Status Bar Customization attempts to trick users into thinking there is a fake URL visible in the status bar. Searching the source code of the website for events such as "on Mouse over" that could change the status bar is the detection process.
- 3.4. Phishing and authentic websites can be distinguished by website forwarding frequency. In Our dataset, reliable websites have never undergone more than one

2) DATA PRE-PROCESSING

- a) Tasks like feature refining and data improvement are essential to data processing. Resolving gaps in

the dataset, eliminating unnecessary information, finding and fixing anomalies or outliers, and balancing out any inconsistencies are all included in the process of data refinement. Data fusion is a tactic that involves combining datasets or databases. One aspect of data transformation is data standardization, which is the process of gathering and organizing data in order to assess a particular dataset. Preparing data for analysis involves a number of steps, such as eliminating unnecessary information, choosing certain examples or situations, and identifying the most pertinent characteristics. By using data reduction techniques, it is possible to reduce the dataset to a smaller size and get more informative study results.

3) TRAIN-TEST SPLIT

- a) In order to effectively utilize the training dataset for identifying phishing websites within the testing dataset, our dataset, comprising 11,054 instances and 31 features, is partitioned into two subsets: the testing set and the training set. Among these features, 30 are independent while 1 is dependent. To streamline training and comprehension of the dataset, 30% of the data is allocated to the testing set.

4) MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHM

- a) In this case, three different machine learning classification models are used:

i) CatBoost Classifier:

CatBoost classifiers are a type of machine learning algorithms that combine several weak learning models to create a robust predictive model. CatBoost often makes use of decision trees. CatBoost and other boosting algorithms are essential for maintaining the proper ratio of variance to bias. In contrast to bagging algorithms, which only address high variance, boosting techniques target bias in addition to variance, making them more efficient.

ii) SVM or Support Vector Machine:

In the field of machine learning, support vector machines are well known. They make up a well-known, straightforward, and easily implementable classification model based on supervised learning. The architecture of SVM is tree-like, with leaf nodes representing results, branching indicating decision-making routes, and internal nodes representing dataset attributes. In SVM, decisions are based on the qualities of the dataset.

iii) Classifier using Random Forest

One popular machine learning technique that is widely used in predictive analytics is Random Forest. It is used to illustrate data graphically and clarify the relationship between a variable and one

or more variable-varying independent variables, whether they are nominal, ordinal, interval,

Fig. 2. Phishing Count in pie chart

ratio level variables. Because it takes into account several variables, Random Forest is skilled at forecasting the likelihood of binary responses. Typically, it is used to forecast results.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULT

A Kaggle dataset was utilized to train various machine learning classifiers aiming to identify phishing websites. Within the Python Jupyter environment, the dataset, comprising 11,054 instances and 32 features, was imported into a Pandas dataframe. Exploration of the dataset unveiled its structure and characteristics. Feature correlation was evaluated through a heatmap, facilitating the identification of potential relationships between features, as illustrated in Figure 1. Requirements Gathering

Fig. 1. Correlation heatmap

Classifiers	Accuracy	f1_score	Recall	Precision
CatBoost Classifier	0.967	0.971	0.978	0.964
Random Forest	0.968	0.969	0.978	0.965
Support Vector Machine	0.946	0.953	0.97	0.936

Table 1. Comparison Table

By showing the ratio of phishing cases to non-phishing cases in the dataset, the pie chart in Figure 2 depicts the distribution of phishing websites.

Both independent and dependent features were separated in the dataset pre-processing stage. An 80-20 ratio was used to divide the data into training and testing sets. The efficacy of several classification models, such as the CatBoost Classifier, Support Vector Machine, and Random Forest, was assessed using a variety of measures, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. To get the best results, the models' hyper parameters were adjusted.

The model for identifying phishing websites is evaluated and trained using a variety of classifier and ensemble techniques in order to guarantee the maximum degree of accuracy. Each algorithm displays its estimated accuracy after finishing its analysis. Table 1 pits these algorithms against one another to see which one achieves the best accuracy rate

Fig. 4. Accuracy vs. Estimators in Random Forest

Fig. 5. Classification report of Random Forest

Fig. 6. Feature importance in the model

Fig. 7. Comparison of all ML algorithms.

Out of all the models tested, the CatBoost Classifier with certain max_depth and learning_rate configurations showed the best accuracy. Furthermore, we were able to identify the most significant characteristics in the model's predictions by visualizing feature importance, as shown in Figure 7.

V. RESULT

Fig.8. Output Result of trusted site

Fig. 9. Output Result of fake site

VI. CONCLUSION

By using machine learning classification models, this work aims to enhance the detection of phishing websites. Using CatBoost classifiers, we can get 97.4% detection accuracy, but Random Forest can only muster 93.4%. Phishing is a serious risk when using the internet. The method developed might be a useful resource for identifying websites and could encourage the creation of more robust anti-phishing techniques in the future.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

Future scope can be the exploration of ensemble methods could be undertaken, possibly incorporating techniques like stacking or blending to combine the strengths of multiple models. Additionally, deeper investigation into feature engineering may be pursued, with a focus on extracting more meaningful features from the URLs or utilizing natural language processing techniques to analyze text content. Implementation of anomaly detection algorithms could enhance the model's capability to detect previously unseen types of phishing attacks. Furthermore, consideration might be given to integrating real-time data streams and deploying the model in a production environment, possibly as part of a web browser extension or an API service, to provide users with proactive protection against phishing threats. Regularly updating the model with new data and monitoring its performance will be crucial for ensuring ongoing effectiveness in the ever-evolving landscape of cyber threats.

VIII. REFERENCES

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